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FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TERRITORY OF THE CITY

Khaydarov Shokhbozjan Zukhridin ugli

The teacher of Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering University ,

e-mail: xshoxbozjon@mail.ru

Berdikulov Azamat Adhamovich

The teacher of Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering University

Abstract: *in this article, k is the number of op socio-economic, demographic, natural-geographic and economic factors, indicating large changes in the development of the territory of the city from the effects of the main factors are considered in the context of market reforms and regulation of urban development activities mechanisms.*

Keywords: *city, population, natural factors, improvement, ecology, natural relief there.*

The process of urban planning is a complex, multifaceted problem, and it is dependent on a number of factors. The effects of the factors are not permanent. It varies, from a type a man had two sons, the two share some factor value increased, while others decrease or disappear altogether. The biggest change will take place at the exchange in the development of their relationship. It can also be observed in the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Numerous socio-economic, demographic, natural-geographic and economic factors in the development of the territory of the city from the effects of the main factors indicating large changes in the context of market reforms and regulation of urban development activities mechanisms are considered below.

Natural-geographical factors. The development of the production activities of life and work to ensure the effective use of natural resources from the territories of the population and committed to defining certain forms in a certain place. Human nature live modified work as a result of the media, the conditions necessary for the development of the society of permanent and turns.

The republic of the major factors influencing the development of the city and the region is the following: the climate, the soil and the hydrographic conditions of the place, which will determine the productivity of all agricultural production; industrial production, which serves as the base of useful minerals and fuel- energy resources; the development of a natural form of transport and communications are defining. To the life and work of the man of influencing natural-climatic factors are of great

importance also incredibly (temperature, wind and moisture regime; provide clean drinking water; the relief of the place; construction seismo geological conditions, including those instances may occur) . These last a number of factors, primarily on the width of the form shows the effect of particular settlements.

Be gathered to the place as a city of population, on the one hand allow for large humans separate from nature started to collect quarters, on the second hand around the media while "natural" is not spotted around the powerful effects of media to allow for some of the biggest commercial artificial and natural opposite of quarters I put in one another.

For the city in the first place out of the defense communications comfortable with communication and organization options. Media in quarters artificially provide water, and ventilation problems become insolation media. Therefore, the ancient city is often embodied in the edge of the river. River communication is the limit of defense is served at the same time and it provides the source of drinking water. The relief of the place, which form in many ways determines the point of living of the population.

The placement of the population landscape mandatory adaptation technique in conjunction with the development of natural forms depending on changing conditions. In the meantime, the artificial planting in combination with hydrological changes with the speed of change was also relief. However, such effects are also economic, and aesthetic aspects of the existing landscape, including the aspiration to maintain the value of the limit is able to according to its purpose. Therefore, in those

instances it or not this nature of a group of settlements see the "picture" of the city will determine the particular limit. The natural landscape architectural-planning at the project level, the primary basis of the solution brings most of the universities.

Demographic factors. Population and labor resources in the form of urban planning is important - the development of cities and other settlements of regional planning as a factor bearing base. In the planned economy, the regulation of migration and natural growth of the population at sustainable levels 20-25 years into the future forecast of the law of the number of results. Labor impaired balance, increased mobility of the regional population, unregulated migration, unemployment and full employment of the population, the population with the prospects of today may be planning to remain unsecured after the old style.

Therefore, a planning document of the prospects of development of the method will also change. Population of the republic in the general plan of the project and regional planning, as well as of the general plan of the city with stand on a periodic basis to correct them taking into account the short and medium term, it is necessary to allow you to develop the true position. In the approval of development projects as one of the key indicators of construction "the amount of new working places" it is necessary to take into account performance. You can make this indicator to allocate land to comply with the condition.

Economic factors. The market economy, especially in the localities much more rapidly in the case creates a source for the use of land, and this, in turn, will cause violation of natural media.

The territory of the city to the growth of proportional pollution of soil, water sources, air atmosphere to be denied, and the violation natural relief cover on disposal on industrial and household waste, noise, radiation and electromagnetic radiation on the fight with the will to solve problems.

One of the environmental security of the country, and even the city did not become the country's problem, it becomes a global problem. Urban planning land use planning this from the factors of a certain type to limit, the engineer of the infrastructure for the creation,

by way of special protection and restoration, it is necessary to take into account the planning of measures.

At the same time the urban development of the theory of the development processes of cities and settlements nesting population study of regional development in collaboration with other sciences and other settlements on the fundamental knowledge legal shape.

A democratic society in the context of the implementation of urban development projects on the basis of a specific plan to be the basis of land use planning and implementation of activities different from all-district wide application forms on the basis of state ownership of the land. In this country, the role of science in urban planning, the decision on its effectiveness determines the direction of the company. This, in turn, the socio-economic effect as measured with the sphere of scientific activity, production and social processes as an important element of the regional plan of improvement that is created will determine the responsibility of the theory.

The theory of urban planning and settlements system organization plan a nesting population, socio-economic and natural conditions in connection with their mutual formation, business development and learn the properties show. The organization of the territory of cities and other settlements in urban planning theory in a systematic way to study the basis and dialectic materialism, is to rely on the market economy and the aesthetics of law. Thus, the production and life of the population-the activity plan and the architecture in relation to the general social position in the organization will investigate the appearance of legitimacy .

Urban planning in the event of the following rules, namely it is advisable to rely on the principles:

The first principle in land use and various legal forms from other localities of the city (rent, the constant term and the use of lifetime inheritance possess a wide range of applied to the ground state on the basis of, based on universal ownership. State ownership of land available in the country to be different depending on the network between the development of economic sectors in the city and other localities of the city necessary in

perspective approach to the establishment of the state will determine its distribution. at the same time, the development of market relations, the economy and the reform of the settlements in connection with long-term rentals, hereditary ownership, privatization of land has broad significance.. But all of this is controlled by the state and regulated.

Urban planning of the city and territory legislation on the basis of the population make up the width of the nesting material media. Thus, it follows the use of means:

- various- district regions for use for the purposes of distribution;
- the placement of elements in the system objects and their regional resources;
- objects width- planned organization.

The second principle in a manner suitable to different functional regulation necessary opportunities and urban development of the territory based on the rational distribution. From the use of the territory in terms of urban planning of regional resources to the economy and at the same time different standardization -district communication costs as low as you can to the case, which is compact, the system is designed to create width . It or not this is necessary for the organization of the territory that the life process of these regions is determined by the amount of properties and dimensions. In particular, the size of the territory of the residential complex is required for the rest of the population, to sports, to utilities, sanitary-hygiene is determined according to the requirements. The amount of the territory of the city housing , production, utility - is determined by the size of the region's barns.

Urban planning and optimal placement of the functional elements using various methods, ie in the width of the composition the reduction of spending on the basis of the necessary territory, city or other settlement, a compact much only you can make.

The reduction of both armed led the technical development of the territory required a different way. In particular, for example, the technique of cleaning the pool in the structure of the city Santariya to increase air-protection of the region allows for the decrease: rest areas and the additional costs to the improvement of their capacity increases. The organization of the

various means of mutual harmony will fill themselves in the planned volume. In particular, the necessary objects to the size of the planned territory composition , character, and the territory is related to the level of service of the equipment.

Prosperity in the development of a large area of today's urban planning system in the case of the natural landscape to their new influences in the development of a new form of motivation for the use of the territory. However, it is not a full answer to the principle that regional and compact, giving our methods are also planning our days in the territory of the organization of the territory of the city the main nesting territory and population of the districts of his importance for the development of the design and save the rest.

The width of the city-regional development in terms of environmental condition of one of the most important principles next this media is taken into account. Urban development in general of the whole of the surrounding media to change the social life-oriented place to be adapted to the requirements of the business. Thus, the ecological approach lies at the basis of all planning processes. However, usually associated with the concept of environmental planning is used to set the event on the protection of the environment.

The results of the research in urban planning and environmental direction two: there will be to take into account the effects of environmental conditions and in practical terms. These areas conventionally "nature protection " and " hygienic called" opportunity can have.

The main purpose of one follows:

- the improvement of the existing ice natural environment;
- it happens to the improvement of the urban development process in use;
- environmental stability re-break away given that restore for recovery purposes.

While the main purpose of the two follows:

- balanced complete the image of human development;
- it is also natural, anthropogenic protection from unwanted effects of media also;

— rational planning of the use of a solution in this case, the effects □□reduce.

It is necessary to record it in the city, environment and nature in a holistic way so fills a mutual and mutual link guard each other, they will practically only indicate the problem. Planning are stored in different levels of urban planning in these areas, but they have to assess the options and make decisions differently comparable worth. This explains the effects of the interaction of natural processes and human activities at the regional level, which appear different to each other. The nature in the region at the system level in the population can be considered relatively stable. Locally at the system level in the population (district planning projects) is prone to a large extent the natural environment and human to change that happens in the main function of the internal and external communication to the change of the landscape "edit" from here . Finally, the practical aspects of the city, in the conditions of artificial and natural elements modified from the man who created the main task for this media "management" is , that is, from the natural process in order to develop the city landscape acceptable to use.

Saying see those who have passed the regional level, how high, char thank you no opportunity necessary, but are also great storage options natural existing commitments. At the regional level to the first level is raised in the direction of urban planning and environmental protection of nature. On the contrary, on the basis of a modified primary city full of the natural conditions necessary for daily life conditions to ensure hygiene urban dwellers the second direction from the limit in the first place. This on the one hand to restore the natural elements with a particular way (for example, green plantations) in addition, on the second hand the city's planning, building and also by way of providing the engineer is achieved. Thus, in the modern city engineering is so great that it is the role of the system, the terminal complex, some experts (environmental infrastructure) as a sign of China. The use of direction in the city the capacity to keep the natural process of nature protection, for example, natural aeration of the territory of the city, the construction work was directed to keep insolation and others.

The territory of the natural, socio-economic and environmental conditions to take into account the principle of the development of the territory of the city is also important in the development of a planning document. Territorial settlements and choose your footprint on the basis of the size of them largely to the relief of the place and the procedure for land use and geological arrangement, hydrography , and the quality of the soil is dependent on the other. The territory of development of natural factors such conditions, the conditions of urban development is unsuitable for the development of the settlements in this area and eventually will determine that. The opportunity to provide the raw materials to the production, their products and the consumer comfortable with the place of production associated with this area, and for them the capacity to attract the necessary resources to create conditions acceptable to labor and employment, and the nature of the process to provide a wide selection of socio-economic conditions also plays an important role in the process of territorial planning of the settlements.

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